

THE ROLE OF THE ORGANIZATION OF TURKIC STATES IN THE MODERN SYSTEM OF INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS

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Abstract: Today, the Organization of Turkic States (OTS) is considering the development of its own program and strategy. One of the main factors making this a necessity is the collapse of the values and principles once presented by the West. At present, the OTS fulfills the mission of filling the visible ideological gaps by maintaining a balanced diplomatic dynamic among the three power centers — NATO, Russia, and China.

It is expected that during the Shusha discussions, the states represented in the OTS will particularly focus on this issue. The Turkic world possesses a common history, language, culture, and political will that can serve as an ideological umbrella. These factors create the necessity of developing a shared ideological program capable of influencing the disrupted world order.

We are confident that the brotherly countries that are members of the OTS will make full use of the Shusha Summit to further enhance their economic, social, cultural, and ideological standards. From now on, the “great powers” of the world — which are gradually shrinking while recognizing new geopolitical realities — will witness how the OTS gives new impetus to achieving peace, stability, and security in the region and on the international stage.

Keywords: Organization of Turkic States (OTS), Cooperation Council of Turkic-Speaking States, Summit meetings, Regional cooperation, Economic integration, Cultural and scientific cooperation

Introduction

On October 3, 2009, at the 9th Summit of the Heads of State of Turkic-speaking countries held in Nakhchivan, the Cooperation Council of Turkic-Speaking States (CCTS) was established with the participation of Azerbaijan, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, and Turkey (Law of the Republic of Azerbaijan on the Ratification of the Nakhchivan Agreement, 2009).

The purpose of establishing this organization was to strengthen linguistic, historical, and cultural ties among Turkic-speaking countries, to give new impetus to regional cooperation, and to deepen economic and social relations.

The CCTS also created new opportunities for mutual interaction and cooperation at the global level and was regarded as a strategic step toward enabling Turkic-speaking countries to have a stronger voice in the international arena. This institutionalization aimed to enhance coordination and develop common policies in areas such as foreign policy and economic cooperation, while also promoting cultural interaction, including collaboration in the field of science.

The Formation and Development Stages of the Organization of Turkic States

After gaining independence, summit meetings began to be held within the framework of the Turkic world. During the Cold War period, as a result of the bipolar system, the Soviet Union prevented the establishment of close relations between Turkey and the Turkic world. While Turkey was a member of the NATO alliance, the fact that Central Asia and the Caucasus were under Soviet influence was a disadvantage for the Turkic world.

Turkey's inability to establish direct relations with the Turkic republics within the Soviet Union led to the failure to mobilize significant potential. After the collapse of the Soviet Union and the declaration of independence by the Turkic-speaking countries, these states gained the opportunity to establish direct relations. Alongside the process of building national statehood, the Turkic-speaking countries also developed multilateral and multidimensional relations.

The first Summit of the Cooperation Council of Turkic-Speaking States was held in Almaty in October 2011; the second in Bishkek in August 2012; the third in Qabala in August 2013; the fourth in Bodrum in June 2014; the fifth in Astana in September 2015; the sixth in Cholpon-Ata in September 2018; the seventh in Baku in October 2019; the eighth in Istanbul in November 2021; the ninth in Samarkand in November 2022; and the tenth in Astana in November 2023 (OTS, 2021).

In 2021, the name of the Cooperation Council of Turkic-Speaking States was changed to the Organization of Turkic States (OTS) (Akçapa, 2023, pp. 473, 491). The new name of the organization contributed to the expansion of its scope and objectives, giving new form and momentum to cooperation [12].

By addressing the Turkic world from a broader perspective, the OTS has focused on wider areas such as the promotion of economic integration, the support of cultural and scientific projects, and regional security. With this name change, the organization expanded its sphere of activity even further, holding summit meetings aimed at strengthening cooperation and enhancing regional solidarity among Turkic-speaking countries. As a result of these summits, important steps were taken to develop mutual cooperation in economic, trade, cultural, and scientific fields.

Since the organization's first summit held in Almaty in 2011, important decisions have been adopted at all summit meetings to increase cooperation in various fields. Discussions have primarily focused on topics such as economic cooperation, science and education, transport and logistics, tourism, media and information, youth and national sports, and support for small and medium-sized enterprises [3].

On July 6, 2024, the informal Summit of the Heads of State of the Organization of Turkic States (OTS) began its work, attracting significant attention from the media. Alongside the official materials presented, numerous analytical articles, commentaries, and opinions were published in the context of Turkic unity and solidarity [3].

In various media outlets, reports titled "An Informal Summit of the Heads of State of the Organization of Turkic States Held in Shusha" gave extensive coverage to the speeches of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan, Ilham Aliyev, as well as those of other participating heads of state and government.

In his speech, President Ilham Aliyev spoke about Azerbaijan's role in the OTS and the goal of transforming the organization into one of the global power centers of the world: "We cover a vast geographical area; our member countries demonstrate positive demographic dynamics; our military potential has repeatedly proven itself on the battlefield. Our rich natural resources, modern infrastructure for their transportation, transport corridors connecting Central Asia and the Caucasus with the Mediterranean and Black Sea ports, our rich and ancient history and culture — all of these are our great assets. The adherence of our peoples to traditional values and their shared ethnic roots tightly unite our countries. The 21st century must be the century of the development of the Turkic world." (Selim, 2024) Moreover, to achieve the stated goals, Azerbaijan contributed 2 million USD to the OTS Secretariat (Report, 2024).

The Minister of Foreign Affairs of the Republic of Turkey, Hakan Fidan, stated that Shusha is a symbol of Azerbaijan's glorious victory in the 44-day Patriotic War:

"We hope that the ongoing negotiations between Azerbaijan and Armenia will soon conclude with the signing of a peace agreement. We particularly appreciate Azerbaijan's strong determination and positive stance in this process. We are not satisfied with the disproportionate position of some Western countries that openly patronize Armenia and ignore Azerbaijan's concerns. The Turkic world will continue to fully support brotherly Azerbaijan until this process is successfully completed." (Hakan, 2024)

At the summit, President of Kazakhstan Kassym-Jomart Tokayev, President of Kyrgyzstan Sadyr Japarov, President of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev, Vice President of Turkey Cevdet Yılmaz, Prime Minister of Hungary Viktor Orbán, and President of the Turkish Republic of Northern Cyprus Ersin Tatar delivered speeches, discussing the activities of the Organization and the prospects for mutually beneficial and multifaceted cooperation.

The Secretary-General of the Organization of Turkic States, Kubanichbek Omuraliev, highlighted Azerbaijan's contributions to the Organization, noting that an important decision for the further development of the OTS was adopted at the Shusha Summit, and that Azerbaijan allocated 2 million USD to the Organization's budget.

The Chairman of the Council of Elders of the Organization of Turkic States, Binali Yıldırım, emphasized that Shusha is regarded as the spiritual capital of the Turkic World and that the summit held there carried special significance. The Shusha Summit is expected to serve as an important platform for strengthening cooperation and integration among the member states of the Organization of Turkic States and for discussing vital issues related to these countries.

President Ilham Aliyev reminded in one of his speeches that the OTS always needs to be continuously strengthened, emphasizing that Azerbaijan has organized numerous initiatives in this direction and continues to take steps toward a more unified and consolidated future. [13].

The head of state noted that his confidence in this process was not accidental, stating: "Because natural allies lie at the foundation of this organization — and it is our shared history, our common culture, our traditions and customs that dictate this unity" [13].

The Organization of Turkic States: A Platform for Economic Integration and Strategic Cooperation

Azerbaijan attaches special importance to the development of relations among the member states of the Organization of Turkic States (OTS) and consistently focuses on strengthening the unity of the Turkic world. The fact that the Organization was established through the Nakhchivan Agreement is a clear expression of this commitment.

Cooperative relations among the countries represented in the Organization have been established both in multilateral and bilateral formats. So far, numerous meetings have been held between high-level officials of the relevant bodies of the member states within the framework of economic relations, and several business forums have been organized.

During these meetings and business forums, the economic potential and areas of cooperation of the member states were presented. Decisions adopted regarding the improvement of the investment environment, the diversification of the economy, and the creation of working groups on entrepreneurship have drawn attention with their positive outcomes.

At the meetings of the OTS Working Group on Economy held to date, detailed exchanges of views have taken place on the current state of cooperation, opportunities for its expansion, the preparation of the “Turkic Vision – 2040” strategic concept, and other issues of mutual interest.

In addition to political relations, economic cooperation that unites the Turkic-speaking states also plays an important role in the Organization’s activities. It is commendable that economic and trade relations among the Turkic-speaking countries have been expanding year by year.

The fact that the countries of the Turkic world are located along the historical Silk Road enables them to play an important role in the growing trade turnover between the East and the West. According to statistical data, the trade turnover between China and European countries exceeds 1 billion USD per day. The location of the Turkic world countries along this vital trade route creates favorable conditions for the Organization of Turkic States (OTS) to become an economic power in the region [9].

Specifically, the total trade turnover of the OTS member states in the global economy amounts to 536 billion USD, which represents more than 2.8% of the world’s total merchandise trade volume in 2019. In the implementation of foreign trade operations among OTS countries, the

Republic of Turkey ranks first with 84%, followed by Kazakhstan (8%), Turkmenistan (5%), Uzbekistan (3%), and Hungary and Tajikistan jointly (1%) [5].

Turkey’s leading position in this ranking is linked to energy trade turnover. In particular, Turkey is the only OTS member state with a significant share in Azerbaijan’s energy exports. Approximately 17% of Azerbaijan’s natural gas exports and 1% of its crude oil exports are directed to the Republic of Turkey [7].

The 12th Summit of the Organization of Turkic States (OTS) held in Qabala not only symbolized the unity of the Turkic world but also strengthened its role and strategic capabilities within the new international security platform [5]. Despite differences in political systems and economic potential, the leaders of Azerbaijan, Turkey, Uzbekistan, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Turkmenistan, Hungary, and

the Turkish Republic of Northern Cyprus once again delivered important messages and presented proposals, demonstrating growing unity and mutual understanding [7].

The summit was of particular significance due to the signing of the Qabala Declaration, which sets out the cooperation priorities for the coming years, as well as the establishment of the “OTS+” format — a mechanism that will enable the inclusion of new states and partners in

Turkic cooperation. Additionally, the decision to strengthen the International Organization of Turkic Culture (TURKSOY) — the cultural foundation of Turkic identity — held special importance.

Conclusion

Today, the Organization of Turkic States (OTS) is emerging as a structured, politically driven, and globally integrated power platform. The goal is not only to optimize formats of cooperation but also to ensure that the Turkic states act from a unified strategic position in international relations.

The areas of cooperation are not limited to politics and security alone. Within the framework of the OTS, multilateral cooperation is being developed in fields such as economy, trade, energy, transport and logistics, agriculture, culture, tourism, information technologies, space research, and other sectors.

The deepening of solidarity, integration, and mutual trust among the Turkic states is steadily elevating the OTS to the level of a respected international organization. Today, countries around the world recognize this union as a reliable partner for stability and cooperation in the region.

In the future, the Organization of Turkic States (OTS) is expected to evolve into a more closely integrated alliance model in terms of politics, economy, and security — transforming it not only into a platform for Turkic-speaking countries but also into an alternative center of stability for the Eurasian and Middle Eastern regions.

Today, the OTS serves as a platform for political solidarity, but tomorrow it may become a global power center. Leadership, determination, and strategic vision have already been established — now it is time to translate that vision into a shared political and economic reality. This path also signifies the realization of the centuries-old dream of unity cherished by the Turkic peoples

REFERENCES

1. Azərbaycan Şuşada daha bir tarix yazdı: Türk dünyasının birliyini Zirvəyə daşıyan Qarabağ Bəyannaməsi. (2024, 06 iyul). Yenicag.az. <https://yenicag.az/azerbaycansusada-daha-bir-tarixyazdi-turk-dunyasinin-birliyini-zirveye-dasiyan-qarabagbeyannamesi/>
2. Akçapa, M. (2023). Türk Devletleri Teşkilatı'nın Tarihsel Gelişimi: Teşkilatın Dünü, Bugünü ve Yarını [Historical Development of the Organization of Turkish States: Yesterday, Today and Tomorrow of the Organization]. Avrasya Uluslararası Araştırmalar Dergisi, 11(34), 473-491. <https://doi.org/10.33692/avasyad.1223099>
3. AZƏRTAC. (2024, 07 iyul). Şuşada Türk Dövlətləri Təşkilatının Dövlət başçılarının qeyri-rəsmi Zirvə görüşündə Qarabağ Bəyannaməsi imzalanıb. https://azertag.az/xeber/susada_turk_dovletleri_teskilatinin_dovlet_baschilarinin_qeyri_resmi_zirve_gorusunde_qarabag_beyannamesi_imzalanib-3086030

4. APA. (2024, 13 noyabr). Bakıda Azərbaycan, Qazaxıstan və Özbəkistan prezidentlərinin üçtərəfli görüşü olub, sənədlər imzalanıb. <https://apa.az/resmi-xeber/bakidaazerbaycan-qazaxistan-ve-ozbekistan-prezidentlerininucterefli-gorusu-olub-875921>
5. Hüseynova, H (2025, 8 oktyabr) Qəbələ Zirvə Görüşü Türk Dünyasının geosiyasi strategiyasında yeni mərhələdir <https://ikisahil.az/post/610292-qebele-zirve-gorushuturk-dunyasinin-geosiyasi-strategiyasinda-yeni-merheledir>.
6. Nuriyev, A. (2024, 07 iyul). Şuşa Zirvə görüşü – Türk dünyasının mühüm platforma meydanı – Şərh. <https://report.az/xarici-siyaset/susa-zirve-gorusu-turk-dunyasininmuhum-platforma-meydaniserh/>
7. Məmmədov, Z (2025, 6 Oktyabr) Qəbələdəki TDT Zirvə Toplantısı: Türk birliyinin siyasi, iqtisadi və hərbi gücü göstərildi. <https://sherg.az/siyaset/320755>
8. Orucova, N. (2024, 10 avqust). “Yaşıl Dəhliz”: Mərkəzi Asiyadan Azərbaycana və daha sonra Avropaya”. <https://tv.ikisahil.az/post/536105-yashil-dehliz-merkezi-asiyadanazerbaycana-ve-daha-sonraavropaya>
9. Report. (2024, 06 iyul) Şuşada TDT-nin dövlət başçılarının qeyri-rəsmi Zirvə görüşü keçirilib. Prezident İlham Əliyev tədbirdə çıxış edib. <https://report.az/daxili-siyaset/susada-tdtnin-dovletve-hokumet-bascilarinin-qeyri-resmi-zirve-gorusu-baslayib-ilham-eliyev-tedbirdeistirak-edir/>
10. Səlim, N. (2024, 07 iyul). Türk Dövlətləri Təşkilatı Şuşadan dünyaya hansı mesajları verdi? – Şərh. <https://konkret.az/turk-dovletleri-teskilati-susadan-dunyaya-hansi-mesajlari-verdiserh/>
11. TDT. (2021). Türk Devletleri Təşkilatı Zirve Toplantısı. <https://www.turkicstates.org/tr/organizasyon-tarihcesi>
12. “Türkdilli Dövlətlərin Əməkdaşlıq Şurasının yaradılması haqqında” Naxçıvan Sazişinin təsdiq edilməsi barədə Azərbaycan Respublikasının Qanunu. <https://eqanun.az/framework/19038>
13. (2022, 11 noyabr) Səmərqənddə Türk Dövlətləri Təşkilatının IX Zirvə Görüşü keçirilib. <https://president.az/az/articles/view/57816>